

PEDAGOGY

CULTURE OF SPEECH AND LISTENING IN THE PROCESS OF BUSINESS COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Communicative problems cause more and more people's interest. This is a necessary part of the professional competence of specialists in all spheres of activity. A modern specialist must possess knowledge in the field of business and academic communication in order to understand communication partners, establish relationships with them, conduct business talks, negotiations and master the basics of public speaking.

The purpose of teaching the subject "Business and academic communication in the Azerbaijani language" is the formation of students' oral and written business and academic communication skills. To provide knowledge in the field of theory and practice of business and academic communication, based on the most effective methods and forms of business communication, the formation and development of communicative competence, which will allow students to carry out their professional activities in the future, is considered one of the main goals of this subject. Concrete words, grammatical constructions, etc. d. for each message. Such types of speech activity as speaking, writing, listening and reading are the basis of the speech process.

Keywords: communication, oral and written speech, business and academic communication.

The process of speaking or talking means that a person joins the system of mutual social relations in a specific case. However, what distinguishes these two subjects from each other is that the thoughts that dominate the inner existence of the listener at the moment of communication, since the relationship to the subject of the speech is in the form of internal speech, can be fully protected from external influences and remains under the control of the subject. Therefore, there is a direct connection between the concepts of listening and inner speech. At the same time, among the means of verbal communication (speaking, listening, reading and writing), it is important to understand that listening is in an active position, that there are active and passive forms of listening, that communication culture consists of normative, communicative, and ethical components.

As a result of teaching the subject of business and academic communication, students get extensive information about the components of communication culture, the observance of conversational standards and the principle of communication expediency, the activity form of conversation, the fact that listening is a type of communication, the forms of listening, and the improvement of listening skills.[3, 11]

Communication problems are causing more and more interest among people. This is a necessary part of the professional competence of specialists in all fields of activity. A modern specialist should have knowledge in the field of business and academic communication in order to understand the communication partners, establish a relationship with them, conduct business conversations, negotiations and master the basics of mass speech. Specific words, grammatical constructions, etc. for each communication. should be There are types of speech activity, such as speaking, writing, listening and reading, which are the basis of the speech process. The main feature of literary language is standardization. A norm is a uniform, generally accepted use of language elements, rules of use in a certain period. Norms are not invented by scientists, they are supported by the regular

processes and events that occur in the language, the experience of speaking. The main sources of the norm include the works of writers, the language of the media, generally accepted contemporary usage, and the scientific research of linguists.

Norms help preserve the integrity and understanding of the literary language, protect it from the influx of dialect speech, social jargon, and foreign languages. Language norms are changing. This is an objective process that does not depend on the will and desire of individual individuals. According to researchers, this process has intensified in recent decades due to social changes. In the critical period, the logo sphere, that is, the field of speech culture, changes significantly, and this, in turn, shows changes in the social consciousness of the language collective. There are options within the literary norm. This objective norm variation is generally associated with language development.

In the process of literary language development, there are changes towards dialects and other functional types of language. As a rule, norms of written speech are formed earlier than oral expression. Currently, there is a tendency for the convergence of written and oral speech. [5, 62-63]

A language event is considered normative if it is characterized by the following features:

- 1) compliance with the structure of the language;
- 2) mass and regular reproduction in the process of communication;
- 3) public approval and recognition. [2, 87]

Both spontaneous and conscious processes take place in the formation of the speech norm. Spontaneity is associated with the mass and regular use of a certain language norm among native language speakers. Language and discourse are processes of "legitimization" or codification of spontaneous language norms that are consciously dominated by grammars and dictionaries. Coding, etc., fixation of events that develop in the process of social experience, is carried out by philologists. What has been mentioned shows the necessity of following the principle of communication expediency in

speech, therefore, the style of speech should be in accordance with the conditions and goals of communication. Knowing the standards of speech and following the principle of appropriateness of communication is the basis of communication culture. Communication culture consists of three: normative, communicative, ethical components, and the main criteria are: 1. Communicative expediency. It is not enough to speak or write correctly, it is important to be aware of the stylistics of words and expressions in order to be able to use them in appropriate communicative situations. 2. Accuracy of statement. Here, two aspects are considered: a) accuracy in the process of reflecting reality and b) accuracy in expressing ideas in one word. The first aspect is related to the authenticity of the speech (true or false). In the second aspect, the following shortcomings are possible: lack of concreteness, confusion. 3. Sequence of presentation. The statement should reflect the logic of reality, the logic of thought and should be characterized by the logic of speech expression. Logical thinking should reflect the facts and relationships of reality (cause-effect, difference-similarity, etc.). The violation of the logic of speech expression is also manifested in the wrong division of the written text into paragraphs. 4. Communicative aesthetics. This is manifested in the rejection by the literary language of means of expression that insult the honor and dignity of a person. 5. Compatibility. The relevance of certain language means depends on the context, situation, and psychological characteristics of the interlocutor's personality. The saying "They don't talk about the rope in the hanged man's house" reflects the essence of this principle very well. [3, 115]

Listening is one of the forms of human activity, like the process of speaking. Hearing and listening cannot be equated. We note that we hear a lot even when we don't want to. If numerous sounds are included in this series, we can say that a person lives in the world of sounds in the true sense. But since the ear is constantly exposed to external sounds, a unique adaptation process takes place. More precisely, the effect of "inaudibility" is created in the vortex of sounds. If every sound (speech) that we care about acts as a source of information for us, it encourages us to listen.

Listening is a conscious activity of a person. This effort comes from the need for information of a person, who is a social being, or from the desire of reality to influence events and processes. Also, the attitude of the parties to each other is reflected in the hearing (agreement, inner feeling of sympathy, disgust, etc.).

Whether we like it or not, listening is a vital necessity. Science has proven that three-quarters of human communication is speaking and listening. It should be noted that among the means of verbal communication (speaking, listening, reading and writing), listening is in the active position.

The famous philosopher Leibniz writes that "... I am ready to travel twenty miles to listen to my worst enemy, if only I can learn something from him." [6, 10]

It is true that listening is important for learning, but it is not essential. For example, any information can be learned by reading from a newspaper (magazine,

book) page or by observing an event live (while watching a football game in a stadium). This suggests that other means than listening can be important as a means of understanding. However, there are spheres of human activity in which it is impossible to do without lively conversation. If there is a conversation, then there is also an addressee (listener).

In many cases, communication is compared in a two-way way. Since solving any problem requires mutual effort, the listening party should also play its role. Sometimes it is assumed that the listening party is passive. In fact, this misconception contradicts the culture of listening. Because even when a person "takes water in his mouth" and remains silent, his attitude towards the subject of the speech should not be considered equal to zero. It is possible that by using non-verbal means, the listener confirms what was said, expresses his agreement and displeasure with gestures.

The process of speaking or talking means that a person joins the system of mutual social relations in a specific case. However, what distinguishes these two subjects from each other is that the thoughts that dominate the inner being of the listener at the moment of communication, and the relationship to the subject of the speech is in the form of internal speech, can be completely protected from external influences. Therefore, there is a direct connection between the concepts of listening and inner speech. [2, 94-95]

Among the numerous forms of listening in recent times, there is talk of male or female listening forms. There are gender characteristics and mentality factors in this style of approach. It must be admitted that the positive qualities of women in the listening process are higher than those of men. It turns out that a subtle creature is also more sensitive. This sensitivity is observed by women's preference for empathic listening. Empathic listening is also important in defining women's social roles (educator, doctor, psychologist, etc.).

In the history of Azerbaijani diplomacy, it is possible to find the names of female diplomats even in the Middle Ages. Sara Khatun, the mother of Aggoyunlu ruler Uzun Hasan, and his wife Daspina Khatun were famous for their negotiation skills. In later times, the Azerbaijani woman impressed even the Europeans with her skill.

The French traveler, ethnographer and writer Alexandre Dumas (father Dumas) skillfully wrote about his meeting and negotiations with Khursudbanu Natanvan, the khan's daughter in Baku, that there was a very strict discipline in this family. Children learn to speak in the presence of adults. The lady of the house was a real noble. It is true that women have not been given much space in the diplomatic arena. Observations of the present day allow us to confirm that the activity of women in the spheres of foreign relations and diplomacy is strengthening. The recent increase in the number of women among the ambassadors confirms that such predictions are in line with reality.

It is difficult to evaluate the speech process, which is a complex psychophysiological phenomenon, without listening. It is believed that men are attentive only for 15-20 seconds. In the following moments, they internally look for a moment to intervene on the subject

of the speech. This means that men tend to listen reflexively. Therefore, men have some difficulty in communicating with women. However, since the listening style is the same when a man talks to a man, abnormal elements that do not meet ethical requirements are not observed. The same is true when a woman interacts with a woman. Observations show that men interrupt women twice as often. Undoubtedly, this is a very bad and unethical habit. [8, 25]

Thus, listening should also be explained by the concept of space and the relations between the parties at this time. Communication between the speaker and the listener at a certain distance should be in accordance with ethical criteria. As a result of teaching the subject of business and academic communication, students get extensive information about the components of communication culture, the observance of speech standards and the principle of communication expediency, the activity form of speech, the fact that listening is a type of communication, the forms of listening, and the improvement of listening skills. At the same time, they learn that listening is in an active position among the means of verbal communication (speaking, listening, reading and writing), but also the existence of active

and passive forms of listening, and that communication culture consists of normative, communicative, and ethical components.

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